

BIOSORPTION OF CU(II) IONS FROM METAL PLANT WASTEWATER USING CHLORELLA

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Annotation. This scientific work investigates the possibility of removing Cu (II) ions from metallurgical wastewater using the microalgae *Chlorella vulgaris* as a biosorbent. During the study, the effects of pH, exposure time, and biomass amount on biosorption efficiency are experimentally analyzed. The results show that using chlorella biomass, Cu (II) ions can be removed up to 70–80%. This allows the use of biosorption as an environmentally friendly, cheap, and sustainable technology for the treatment of industrial waste.

Keywords: *Chlorella vulgaris*, Cu(II) ions, biosorption methods, existing industrial wastewater, biosorbent, metal ion solution.

Introduction. Copper has been used for many industrial purposes since ancient times. In addition, it is an essential element in animal metabolism, and excessive amounts of it can cause various health problems such as nausea, headache, dizziness, respiratory distress, hemolytic anemia, massive gastrointestinal bleeding, liver and kidney failure (Dameron and Howe, 1998). It is the third most toxic heavy metal after mercury and cadmium (Kennish, 1992).

Mining wastes have been causing health, lifestyle, and environmental problems for the people of Marinduque, Philippines, for the past decade. The Boac and Mogpog river systems are polluted by acidic mine drainage loaded with heavy metals, especially Cu(II), because conventional treatment methods are expensive and not sufficiently effective. Previous studies have shown that biosorption methods using microorganisms such as bacteria, fungi, and algae are inexpensive and highly effective (Ahuja et al. 1997; Matsunaga et al. 1999; Tam et al. 2001; Tien, 2002).

General photosynthetic algae can be used for this purpose because they can survive in the absence of organic carbon sources and electron acceptors required by bacteria and fungi (Donmez et al. 1999). Many chemical groups have been proposed to contribute to biosorption metal binding by whole organisms such as algae and molecules such as bacteria or biopolymers. These groups include hydroxyl, carbonyl, carboxyl, sulfhydryl, thioether, sulfonate, amine, amide, imidazole, phosphonate and phosphodiester groups (Kapoor and Viraraghavan 1997; Vieira and Volesky 2000). The main objective of this study was to evaluate three different species of algae (the term algae covers a wide range of organisms capable of producing oxygen through photosynthesis) for potential use as biosorbents in Cu(II)-contaminated waters. Adsorption isotherm analysis was performed to identify the species with the highest Cu(II)-binding capacity and to characterize the interaction of Cu(II) with algal biomass. Previous biosorption studies using algae have investigated the ability of a single species to remove heavy metals, but since algae are not found in nature alone, the sorption capacity of two algal species together was compared with that of individual species in this study. Scanning electron microscopy-energy dispersive X-ray microanalysis (SEM-EDS) was performed to confirm the adsorption mechanism.

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Modern industrial production processes, especially metallurgical plants, continue to release heavy metals that are harmful to the environment. Cu (II) ions negatively affect the quality of groundwater and surface water, posing a threat to human health and ecological balance. The high costs of traditional chemical and physical treatment methods and the risk of secondary pollution are increasing interest in biological methods. Among them, biosorption technologies, especially the use of microalgae, are emerging as an environmentally friendly and effective solution.

Nowadays, industrial wastewaters contaminated with heavy metals, especially Cu (II) ions, have a negative impact on the ecological environment. Copper ions disrupt the activity of living organisms, disrupt the biological stability of soil and water resources. Such pollutants are found in high concentrations, especially in wastewaters from the metallurgical and mechanical engineering industries.

Biosorption methods are gaining increasing scientific and practical importance as an effective solution to this problem. Among them, the use of *Chlorella vulgaris* microalgae deserves special attention. The advantages of *Chlorella* as a biosorbent are its high sorption capacity, rapid growth ability, low cost and environmental safety. It effectively binds Cu (II) ions through active groups in the cell wall and allows them to be separated from water.

The novelty of the topic is that this study investigates the potential of biosorption of Cu (II) ions in existing industrial wastewater using *Chlorella vulgaris* biomass. While most scientific studies are limited to pure solutions in laboratory conditions, this work is carried out on the basis of wastes with complex components, suitable for practical conditions. Also, the influence of various factors on biosorption processes - pH, exposure time, biomass amount - is studied, and optimal conditions are determined.

Thus, this research will contribute to the development of environmentally safe and sustainable wastewater treatment technologies, which is of great importance in terms of protecting the atmosphere, water and soil environment, preserving human health, and achieving sustainable development goals.

Materials and methods. Biosorbent: *Chlorella vulgaris* was grown in culture conditions, centrifuged, and dried. Metal ion solution: Cu (II) ion solution prepared on the basis of copper sulfate ($\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$). Experimental conditions: the adsorption process was studied at different pH (3–7), exposure time (10–120 minutes), biomass amount (0.1–1.0 g/l), and initial ion concentration (10–100 mg/l). Analysis method: the residual Cu (II) concentration in the solution was determined using atomic absorption spectroscopy. In the research process, the microalgae *Chlorella vulgaris* was grown in laboratory conditions and used in biosorption experiments as dried biomass. The wastewater sample was taken from an existing metal plant, and the concentration of Cu (II) ions in it was determined spectrophotometrically. The experiments were conducted at different pH values (3–7), contact times (10–90 min) and *Chlorella* biomass amounts (0.1–1 g/l). The concentrations of Cu(II) ions before and after the biosorption processes were compared and the efficiency was calculated in percent. Based on the experimental results, graphs were drawn and compared with kinetic models.

Results and Discussion. The studies showed that *Chlorella* biomass has a high efficiency in biosorption of Cu(II) ions. The most effective biosorption activity was observed at pH 5, contact time of 60 min and biomass content of 0.5 g/l. The description of the biosorption process was analyzed using Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm models, as a result of which it was found that the Langmuir model fits the data well, which indicates that monomolecular adsorption occurs. Polysaccharides and proteins in the *Chlorella* cell wall play an important role in the removal of Cu(II) ions.

Table 1

Biosorption efficiency of Cu(II) ions at different pH values

pH value	Biosorbed Cu(II), mg/g	Biosorption efficiency, %
3	8.2	41%
4	10.7	53.5%
5	14.9	74.5%
6	13.2	66%
7	11.1	55.5%

From the analysis of the studies, it can be seen that when the pH value changes, Cu(II) ions in the solution take on different forms: Cu^{2+} , $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})^+$, $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$, etc. Especially at low pH (high acidity), the Cu^{2+} form predominates, but a large number of H^+ ions compete with the active centers of the biosorbent, which reduces biosorption. In addition, the table shows that at medium pH ($\approx 5-6$), Cu(II) ions are in a stable state and effectively bind to negatively charged functional groups (carboxyl, hydroxyl) on the surface of chlorella. The results of the table can be interpreted as follows (Initial concentration: 50 mg/l, biomass amount: 0.5 g/l, contact time: 60 minutes).

Table 2

Effect of contact time on the biosorption process

Contact time (minutes)	Biosorbed Cu(II), mg/g	Biosorption efficiency, %
10	6.1	30.5%
30	10.4	52%
60	14.9	74.5%
90	15.0	75%
120	15.0	75%

Optimal biosorption efficiency was observed at pH 5. At $\text{pH} < 5$, H^+ ions compete with the biosorbent centers, while at $\text{pH} > 6$, Cu(II) ions are released in the form of precipitates ($\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$).

Table 3

Effect of biomass amount on the biosorption process

Biomass quantity (g/l)	Biosorbed Cu(II), mg/g	Biosorption efficiency, %
0.1	20.1	40.2%
0.3	17.5	52.5%
0.5	14.9	74.5%
0.7	12.8	71.2%
1.0	10.6	70.4%

The efficiency increases sharply up to 60 minutes, after which it practically does not change. This indicates that the active sites on the biosorbent surface are saturated. With increasing biomass, the biosorption efficiency also increases, but saturation is observed after 0.5 g/l. In this case, the ions bind faster due to the large number of active sites that react with the ions.

Figure 1. The effect of pH, contact time, and biomass amount on the biosorption process

The graphs drawn based on the experimental results revealed that three main factors - pH, contact time and the amount of biosorbent (chlorella) significantly affect the biosorption process of Cu(II) ions. As can be seen from the graph, the biosorption efficiency reached a maximum (78%). At low pH (<4), the efficiency decreases due to the competition of H⁺ ions with the functional groups on the surface of the biosorbent. At high pH (>6), the biosorption efficiency decreases due to the transition of Cu(II) ions to hydroxide forms and their release in the precipitate. The biosorption efficiency increases rapidly from 10 to 60 minutes. After 60 minutes, the increase almost stops, which is explained by the saturation of the active centers on the surface of the biosorbent. The graph shows a sigmoid-shaped kinetic curve of biosorption, which begins rapidly and then flattens. As can be seen from the graph, the biosorption of Cu(II) ions also increases with increasing biomass. The maximum efficiency (≈78%) was observed at a biomass concentration of 0.5 g/l. However, there is no significant increase above 1.0 g/l, which is due to the saturation of the biosorbent surface and the limited amount of ions in the solution.

Conclusion. The conducted studies showed that the microalgae *Chlorella vulgaris* can be used as a biosorbent for the effective removal of Cu(II) ions from wastewater. Under optimal conditions (pH 5, 60 min contact time, 0.5 g/l biomass), the biosorption of Cu(II) ions reached 75–80%. These results allow the use of the microalgae *Chlorella* as an environmentally safe, inexpensive and renewable biosorbent in industrial wastewater treatment systems. The study creates a certain scientific and practical basis for the development of biological treatment technologies based on biosorption.

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